

A GENERALIZED (G'/G) - EXPANSION METHOD FOR THE LOADED MODIFIED BURGERS–KDV EQUATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6782135>

Keywords : soliton solution, loaded modified Burgers–KdV equation, nonlinear equations, expansion method

This paper is dedicated to find the solutions of the equation of the loaded modified Burgers–KdV equation. It is shown to find the solutions via (G'/G) - expansion method that is one of the most effective way of finding solutions.

Consider the following loaded modified Burgers–KdV equation

$$u_t + pu^2u_x + qu_{xx} - ru_{xxx} + \gamma(t)u(0,t)u_x = 0, \quad (1)$$

where $u(x,t)$ is an unknown function, $x \in R$, $t \geq 0$, $\gamma(t)$ - is the given real continuous function.

Description of the generalized (G'/G)-expansion method

Let us be given a nonlinear partial differential equation in the form below

$$F(u, u_t, u_x, u_{tt}, u_{xx}, u_{xt}, \dots) = 0 \quad (2)$$

with two independent variables x and t . $u = u(x,t)$ is a unknown function, F is a polynomial in q and its partial derivatives in which the highest order derivatives and nonlinear terms are involved. Now we give the main steps of the (G'/G)-expansion method [3]:

Step 1. We look for the u in the travelling form:

$$u(x,t) = u(\xi), \quad \xi = kx - \Omega(t), \quad (3)$$

where k is parameter and $\Omega(t)$ is a continuous function dependent on t . We reduce equation (2) to the following nonlinear ordinary differential equation:

$$P(u, u', u'', u''', \dots) = 0, \quad (4)$$

where P is a polynomial of $q(\xi)$ and its all derivatives $u' = du(\xi)/d\xi$, $u'' = d^2u(\xi)/d\xi^2$, .

Step 2. We assume that the solution of equation (4) has the form:

$$u(\xi) = \sum_{j=0}^m a_j \left(\frac{G'}{G} \right)^j, \quad (5)$$

where $G = G(\xi)$ satisfies the following second order ordinary differential equation

$$G'' + \lambda G' + \mu G = 0, \quad (6)$$

where $G' = dG(\xi)/d\xi$, $G'' = d^2G(\xi)/d\xi^2$ and λ, μ, a_j ($j=1,2,\dots,m$) are constants that can be determined later, provided $a_m \neq 0$.

Step 3. We determine the integer number m by balancing the nonlinear terms of the highest order and the partial product of the highest order of (4).

Step 4. Substitute (5) along with (6) into (4) and collect all terms with the same order of $\left(\frac{G'(\xi)}{G(\xi)}\right)$, the left-hand side of (4) is converted into a polynomial in $\left(\frac{G'(\xi)}{G(\xi)}\right)$. Then, set each coefficient of this polynomial to zero to derive a set of over-determined partial differential equations for a_j ($j=1,2,\dots,m$) and ξ .

Step 5. Substituting the values a_j ($j=1,2,\dots,m$) and ξ as well as the solutions of equation (6) into (5) we have the exact solutions of equation (2).

References:

1. A. Bekir, Application of the (G'/G) -expansion method for nonlinear evolution equations, Phys. Lett. A, 372, 3400 (2008).
2. S. Zhang, J. L. Tong, W. Wang, A generalized (G'/G) -expansion method for the mKdV equation with variable coefficients, Phys. Lett. A, 372, 2254 (2008).
3. M. Wang, X. Li, J. Zhang, The (G'/G) -expansion method and travelling wave solutions of nonlinear evolution equations in mathematical physics, Phys. Lett. A, 372, 417 (2008).